

**A comparative study of Value Added Ratios of Britannia Industries Ltd and
Nestle India Ltd**

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Abstract:

This study has been done with the aim to compare Value Added Statements (VAS) and Value Added Ratio (VAR) of selected 2 FMCG companies namely Britannia Industries Ltd and Nestle India Ltd by using non-probability judgemental technique. To achieve the motive of comparison of VAR, Value Added Statement was prepared by researcher from annual report of both the companies as GVA and NVA has been found out for further analysis and then calculated Ratios that are NVA to Sales ratio, Contribution to Employees to NVA Ratio Contribution to Capital providers to NVA Ratio, Contribution to Government to NVA Ratio, Contribution to owner to NVA Ratio VAS. This study covers five years of research period Starting from 2021-22 to 2025-26. For data analysis T-test is used. This study concluded that there is significant difference between the performance of both the companies.

Keywords: *Value Added Statement (VAS), Gross Value Added (GVA), Net Value Added (NVA), Value Added Ratio (VAR), FMCG (Fast Moving Consumer Goods) Industry*

Introduction:

The concept of Value Added Statement (VAS) is gaining wider attention because of having some its unique features and limitations of conventional accounting method. Value Added Statement disclose value generation and its distribution among of stakeholders like government, employees, owners, and loan providers of the company. It is not a novel concept UK and South Africa used to prepare VAS in 1970-80.

Literature Review:

(Israni & Imrankhan , 2025) Has done comparative study of two textiles and apparel companies namely Bombay Dyeing and Page Industries. Firstly they prepare VAS and then calculated Value Added Ratios from that. For analysis of data T-test has been used by researchers. The study period is five years from 2019 to 2023. Measure VAR showing no significant difference between both the companies.

(Riahi-Belkaoui, 1996) Defines in his book Value Added Reporting as superior in compare of conventional accounting to indicate wealth creation for capital providers, stakeholders and policymakers. This VAR can be more helpful to take decisions regarding investment. Empirical analysis done in Europe supports viewpoint of an author and supports its implementation in US also.

(Bagieńska, 2017) This article focus on how VAS offer expanded viewpoint on performance of an enterprise as VAS show value creation and distribution of value among its stakeholders. Traditional accounting mostly focus on information regarding shareholders but don't share information about stakeholders. This study concluded that inclusion of VAS with an integrated reporting enhance disclosure quality.

Objectives of the study:

- To prepare VAS and calculate the Gross Value Added (GVA) and Net Value Added (NVA) of selected companies.
- To compare Value Added Ratio (VAR) of both the companies.

Research Methodology:

Sample selection:

Researcher has selected 2 samples from FMCG Industry with the help of Non Probability Judgemental Method.

Top 2 companies are selected on the basis of Market capitalization on 27 may, 2026. Which are Nestle India Ltd and Britannia Industries Ltd.

Sample profile:

Nestle India Ltd:

Nestle was established on 28 March, 1959. This is an Indian Subsidiary of Swiss Multinational Company, Nestle. In Moga, Punjab ; Nestle India Ltd has started its first facility for milk Industry. Currently Nestle is operating in beverages, dairy, , foods sectors. It is having 9 production facilities across India.

Britannia Industries Ltd:

A small group of British Businessmen has established Britannia Industries Ltd in 1892. In the starting phase, It was producing biscuits only. In 1918, It was renamed as Britannia Biscuits Company Limited by C.H. Holmes when they becomes partner in the company. In 1979, it was again renamed as Britannia Industries Ltd.

Period of the study:

Period of the study is 5 years from 2021-22 to 2025-26.

Hypotheses of the study:

H_0 = There is no significant difference in NVA to Sales ratio of both the companies during the study period.

H_1 = There is significant difference in NVA to Sales ratio of both the companies during the study period.

H_0 = There is no significant difference in contribution to employees to NVA ratio of both the companies during the study period.

H_1 = There is significant difference in contribution to employees to NVA of both the companies during the study period.

H_0 = There is no significant difference in contribution to government to NVA ratio of both the companies during the study period.

H_1 = There is significant difference in contribution to government to NVA ratio of both the companies during the study period.

H_0 = There is no significant difference in contribution to capital providers to NVA ratio of both the companies during the study period.

H_1 = There is significant difference in contribution to capital providers to NVA ratio of both the companies during the study period.

H_0 = There is no significant difference in contribution to owner to NVA ratio of both the companies during the study period.

H_1 = There is significant difference in contribution to owner to NVA ratio of both the companies during the study period.

Data Collection

For the analysis of data, data has been collected from annual report of both the companies respectively for the 5 years ranging from 2021-22 to 2025-26.

Data Analysis

To fulfil the objectives, 2 tools namely Value Added Ratio (VAR) and T-test statistical tool has been used.

Value Added Ratio (VAR):

VAR is accounting ratio that represent relationship between different elements of VAS.

T-Test:

T – test is a statistical parametric test that is used for the comparison between means of 2 samples.

Table no. 1 Value Added Statement (VAS) of Nestle India Ltd for 5 Year

Generation of value	2021-22	2022-23	2023-24	2024-25	2025-26
Net Sales	16,896.96	19,126.30	24,393.89	20,201.56	23,154.60
ADD: Change in Stock	-250.27	-40.01	-45.68	-139.66	-168.23
Value of Production	16,646.69	19,086.29	24,348.21	20,061.90	22,986.37
ADD: Other Income	101	121.21	147.96	56.86	40.35
Gross Output	16,747.69	19,207.50	24,496.17	20,118.76	23,026.72
LESS: Goods & Services Brought-In					
(A) Material Used	7,652.11	8054.95	10216.88	8390.15	9814.04
(B) Other Expenditure	3,646.57	4,716.88	5,966.09	4,603.26	5,579.68
GVA	5449.01	6435.67	8313.2	7125.35	7633
LESS: Depreciation	403.01	428.91	537.78	518.17	699.23
NVA	5046	6006.76	7775.42	6607.18	6933.77
Distribution of Value					
To Employees	1635.46	1849.18	2336.06	2023.71	2165.81
To Providers of Loan Capital	154.57	119.29	145.49	136	158.31
To Government	865.45	1039.62	1356.03	1132.97	1065.05
To Owners	2390.52	2998.67	3937.84	3314.5	3544.6
NVA	5046	6006.76	7775.42	6607.18	6933.77

(source: annual report of Nesle India)

Table no. 2 Value Added Statement (VAS) of Britannia Industries Ltd for 5 Year

Generation of value	2021-22	2022-23	2023-24	2024-25	2025-26
Net Sales	13,371.62	15,618.42	16,186.08	17,295.92	18,445.82
ADD: Change in Stock	-73.96	-82.13	-0.01	-67.96	-21.42
Value of Production	13,297.66	15,536.29	16,186.07	17,227.96	18,424.40
ADD: Other Income	359.43	220.59	210.11	250.68	318.44
Gross Output	13,657.09	15,756.88	16,396.18	17,478.64	18,742.84
LESS: Goods & Services Brought-In					
(A) Material Used	6,366.31	7084.09	7394.74	8608.64	9045.68
(B) Other Expenditure	4,428.63	4,962.12	5,158.13	4,725.76	5,320.21
GVA	2,862.15	3,710.67	3,843.31	4,144.24	4,376.95
LESS: Depreciation	170.01	195.1	271.19	284.67	305.34
NVA	2692.14	3515.57	3572.12	3859.57	4071.61
Distribution of Value					
To Employees	413.56	520.55	565.28	854.7	667.47
To Providers of Loan Capital	133.46	154.95	151.4	137.1	110.8
To Government	541.93	700.77	773.39	737.05	731.62
To Owners	1603.19	2139.3	2082.05	2130.72	2561.72
NVA	2692.14	3515.57	3572.12	3859.57	4071.61

(source: annual report of Britannia Industries Ltd)

Table no. 3 NVA to Sales Ratio

Nesle India				Britannia Industries Ltd			
Year	NVA (RS.)	Sales (Rs.)	NVA/Sales*100	Year	NVA (RS.)	Sales (Rs.)	NVA/Sales*100
2021-22	5046	16896.96	29.86	2021-22	2692.14	13371.62	20.13
2022-23	6006.76	19126.3	31.40	2022-23	3515.57	15618.42	22.50
2023-24	7775.42	24393.9	31.87	2023-24	3572.12	16186.08	22.06
2024-25	6607.18	20201.6	32.71	2024-25	3859.57	17295.92	22.31
2025-26	6933.77	23154.6	29.94	2025-26	4071.61	18445.82	22.07

(source: annual report of Nestle India Ltd and Britannia Industries Ltd)

Analysis: The above table is showing numerical data of NVA to Sales ratios of both the companies. A mixed trend can be observed in both the companies. Nestle India Ltd is having highest ratio in 2024-25 at 32.71% and lowest at 29.86 % in 2021-22. As Britannia Industries Ltd is having highest ratio at 22.50% in 2022-23 and lowest in 2021-22 at 20.13%. After analysis both the companies we can conclude that Britannia Industries Ltd has more consistency in NVA to Sales ratio than Nestle India Ltd.

Table no. 4 contribution to employees to NVA ratio

Nesle India				Britannia Industries Ltd			
Year	Contri. to emp.	NVA (Rs.)	NVA /Contri. to Emp.*100	Year	Contri. to emp.	NVA (Rs.)	NVA/ Contribution to Emp*100
2021-22	1635.46	5046	32.41	2021-22	413.56	2692.14	15.36
2022-23	1849.18	6006.76	30.78	2022-23	520.55	3515.57	14.80
2023-24	2336.06	7775.42	30.04	2023-24	565.28	3572.12	15.82
2024-25	2023.71	6607.18	30.63	2024-25	854.7	3859.57	22.14
2025-26	2165.81	6933.77	31.23	2025-26	667.47	4071.61	16.39

(source: annual report of Nestle India Ltd and Britannia Industries Ltd)

Analysis: This table no. 4 is showing Contribution to employees to NVA ratio. This ratio suggests the proportion of NVA utilized on employees. After analysis of this data, we can see that the highest ratio is at 32.41% in 2021-22 and lowest in 2023-23 at 30.04% of Nestle India Ltd. Britannia Industries Ltd is having its highest and lowest ratio at 22.14% in 2024-25 and 14.80% in 2022-23 respectively. We can conclude that Nestle India Ltd is contributing more NVA towards its employees than Britannia Industries Ltd. And Nestle India Ltd is also having more stability in ratio than Britannia Industries Ltd.

Table no. 5 Contribution to Capital providers to NVA ratio

Nesle India				Britannia Industries Ltd			
Year	Contri. To capital providers	NVA (Rs.)	NVA/ Contri. To cap. Pro.*100	Year	Contri. To cap. Pro.	NVA (Rs.)	NVA/ Contri. To cap. Pro.*100
2021-22	154.57	5046	3.06	2021-22	133.46	2692.14	4.96
2022-23	119.29	6006.76	1.98	2022-23	154.95	3515.57	4.41
2023-24	145.49	7775.42	1.87	2023-24	151.4	3572.12	4.23
2024-25	136	6607.18	2.05	2024-25	137.1	3859.57	3.55
2025-26	158.31	6933.77	2.28	2025-26	110.8	4071.61	2.72

(source: annual report of Nestle India Ltd and Britannia Industries Ltd)

Analysis: This Table no. 5 is showing the data of Contribution to capital providers to NVA ratio of Nestle India Ltd and Britannia Industries Ltd. The highest point is at 3.06% in 2021-22 and lowest at 1.87% in 2022-23 of Nestle India Ltd. The highest and lowest points of Britannia Industries Ltd are 4.96% in 2021-22 and 2.72% in 2025-26 respectively. Here we can see more consistency in Nestle India Ltd.

Table no. 6 Contribution to Government to NVA ratio

Nesle India				Britannia Industries Ltd			
Year	Contri. to gov.	NVA (Rs.)	NVA/ Contri. to gov.*100	Year	Contri. to gov.	NVA (Rs.)	NVA/ Contri. to gov.*100
2021-22	865.45	5046	17.15	2021-22	541.93	2692.14	20.13
2022-23	1039.62	6006.76	17.30	2022-23	700.77	3515.57	19.93
2023-24	1356.03	7775.42	17.44	2023-24	773.39	3572.12	21.65
2024-25	1132.97	6607.18	17.15	2024-25	737.05	3859.57	19.09
2025-26	1065.05	6933.77	15.36	2025-26	731.62	4071.61	17.96

(source: annual report of Nestle India Ltd and Britannia Industries Ltd)

Analysis: Table no. 6 is showing numerical information of Contribution made to Government to NVA ratio. This ratio suggests the proportion of NVA contributed to the government as a part of Taxes. From this table, we can conclude that the highest ratio is 17.44% in 2023-24 and lowest is 15.36% in 2025-26 of Nestle India Ltd. For Britannia Industries Ltd, the highest point is 21.65% in 2023-24 and lowest at 17.96% in 2025-26. Nestle India Ltd is more consistent than Briannia industries.

Table no. 7 Contribution to Owner to NVA ratio

Nesle India				Britannia Industries Ltd			
Year	Contri. to owner	NVA (Rs.)	NVA/ Contri. to owner*100	Year	Contri. to owner	NVA (Rs.)	NVA/ Contri. to owner*100
2021-22	2390.52	5046	47.37	2021-22	1603.19	2692.14	59.55
2022-23	2998.67	6006.76	49.92	2022-23	2139.3	3515.57	60.85
2023-24	3937.84	7775.42	50.64	2023-24	2082.05	3572.12	58.28
2024-25	3314.5	6607.18	50.16	2024-25	2130.72	3859.57	55.20
2025-26	3544.6	6933.77	51.12	2025-26	2561.72	4071.61	62.91

(source: annual report of Nestle India Ltd and Britannia Industries Ltd)

Analysis: Table no. 7 is showing Contribution to Owners to NVA ratio. This ratio suggests that how much of total value generated by company is allocated among the owners of the company. The highest ratio is at 50.64% in 2023-24 and lowest is 47.37% in 2021-22 of Nestle India Ltd. The highest and lowest ratio of Britannia Industries Ltd are 62.91% in 2025-26 and 55.20% in 2024-25 respectively. We can see more consistent performance of Nestle India Ltd in compare of Britannia Industries Ltd.

Table no. 8 Result of study

RATIO	Table value (for two tail) of t - test	Calculated value of t-test	RESULT
NVA to Sales Ratio	2.31	13.33	H ₀ is rejected
Contribution to Employees to NVA Ratio	2.31	10.13	H ₀ is rejected
Contribution to Government to NVA Ratio	2.31	-3.98	H ₀ is rejected
Contribution to Providers of capital to NVA Ratio	2.31	-3.91	H ₀ is rejected
Contribution to owners to NVA Ratio	2.31	-6.59	H ₀ is rejected

Conclusion:

After analysis, we can see that there is a significant difference between performance of both the companies during the research period covered by researcher. This is because null hypothesis for each ratios has been rejected. Ratios that are NVA to Sales ratio, Contribution to Employees to NVA Ratio Contribution to Capital providers to NVA Ratio, Contribution to Government to NVA Ratio, Contribution to owner to NVA Ratio are used.

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